

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D5.2 - Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 2

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>For cities to upscale their climate neutral and resilience objectives for city-wide implementation, the use of governance instruments is essential. adelphi develops a framework for identifying transformative instruments based on city needs and recommendations on how to proceed specifically on improving transformative governance. Building on the report on D5.1 that described the Governance Framework itself, this report describes the process of its testing with the cities in the upscaling phase and its operationalisation on the UP2030 Service Platform, including the complementary recommendations.</p>			

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Executive summary

In pursuit of their climate neutrality and resilience targets, many European cities need to upscale their pilot initiatives for a city-wide implementation. Going from project-based pilot initiatives to standard practices for city administrations and stakeholders requires effective transformative governance. Under the UP2030 Horizon Europe project, transformative governance – in short – refers to the norms, institutions, and processes used by cities to make and implement decisions on climate neutrality, resilience, justice, and liveability.

The Governance Analysis Framework, based on Bressers et al. (2016), supports cities in assessing what governance arrangements they need to accelerate and solidify their transformation efforts. The framework operationalises the complex concept of governance, making it more meaningful and relevant to transformation practitioners. It breaks down “transformative governance” into five dimensions: goals & perspectives, strategies & instruments, levels & scales, actors & networks, and resources & responsibilities. For each of these dimensions, it offers a way for cities to self-assess their status. This assessment can be done individually or with the actors of city’s choice (e.g. internal municipal actors, external stakeholders) – for which in UP2030 an online questionnaire for the service platform and a workshop methodology were developed and tested, respectively.

Furthermore, the framework offers a list of concise recommendations on how to strengthen the governance structures for transformation, supported by useful material and best practice examples. Several recommendations are particularly relevant for each of the dimensions, so the user can choose to focus on selected dimensions. The recommendations can also be used as a quick checklist to see which aspects are covered better and which actions might still be useful to ramp up the governance arrangements in a particular transformation area.

This report is the second deliverable under this task: while the first deliverable documents the conceptualisation of transformative governance and the ideas on how to create materials and tools for urban practitioners based on this, the present deliverable describes the progress of this effort and gives an overview of the final outputs. It provides a brief recap on the transformative governance concept and its operationalisation in five dimensions (Section 2). Moreover, it goes on to describe how this was transferred into an online questionnaire for the self-assessment, tested in a workshop form with the Pilot City of Budapest on heat management governance and informed the upscaling work with individual Pilot Cities (Section 3). The document concludes with an overview of the recommendations for improving governance, explaining how they provide hints for next steps and examples from UP2030 work (Section 4). The annexes contain the questionnaire and the current version of recommendations (the latter is under revision of the UP2030 consortium until 20 September 2025 in order to make sure that the learnings from the project are reflected appropriately, to be completed by the end of the project).

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package’s (WPs) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with ICLEI and GGGI, among other partners, in WP5 (T5.2, T5.3, T5.4), WP4 (T4.2) and WP2 (T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4). The development of the governance framework has been aligned with the progress on visioning and pathway development, and it has been an integral part of the upscaling phase led by ICLEI. The recommendations include the relevant and publicly available UP2030 experiences as practical guidance for cities who would like to work on transformative governance in the future.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities</p> <p>D5.1. – Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 1</p>	<p>D5.3 – UP2030 Service Platform</p> <p>D5.7 – Online Learning Platform Materials</p>
<p>Mil.5 Cities run first workshop on needs</p> <p>Mil.6 Cities run second workshop on vision</p> <p>Mil.7 Cities establish user stories</p> <p>Mil.8 First meeting of the expert panel on Governance and Policy for climate neutrality in European cities</p> <p>Mil.13 All cities have at least one successful prototype</p>	<p>Mil.14 Cities run fourth workshop on upscale</p> <p>Mil.15 Training programme successful delivery completed</p> <p>Mil.16 Service platform up operative</p>

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
D	Deliverable
GAF	Governance Analysis Framework
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
ICLEI	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability
LAA	Learning and Action Alliance
Mil	Milestone
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
T	Task
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The Governance Analysis Framework (GAF) is part of the UP2030 UP-scaling phase, where “transferability packages and upscaling frameworks related to solutions are prepared to understand and replicate solutions in other cities in Europe and beyond” (Fernandez et al., 2023). Here it relates to the upscaling frameworks, looking into integrative policies, governance barriers as well as multilevel collaboration as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The SUP approach. Source: Fernandez et al. (2023)

In the early phases of the project, it became clear that cities needed more practical guidance on how to use governance effectively to reach their goals of climate neutrality, climate justice, and resilience. Particularly, when looking at upscaling pilot initiatives, a wider (i.e. administrative, societal and economic) and long-term transformation process is required enabling the pathway towards city-wide climate goals.

To support cities in the required transformation process, it is necessary to look at their current governance set-up for the task they are tackling. The framework helps cities analyse their individual strengths and challenges in this regard and gives orientation on possibilities to improve their status, including practical material to start with and best practice examples. The transformative governance framework and material are results of conceptual work by adelphi, feedback from an expert panel, as well as of engaging with the Pilot Cities, both during the framework development and in the upscaling phase of UP2030.

The report provides a brief recap on the transformative governance concept and its operationalisation in five dimensions (Section 2). It goes on to describe how this was transferred into an online questionnaire for the self-assessment, tested in a workshop form with the Pilot City of Budapest that was interested in a governance deep-dive for heat management (12-13 June 2024) and informed the upscaling work with individual Pilot Cities (Section 3). The document then gives an overview of the recommendations for improving governance, explaining how they provide hints for next steps and examples from UP2030 work (Section 4). The conclusion reflects on the role of the task within the project and the outlook for the framework beyond the project. The annexes contain the questionnaire and the current version of recommendations (the latter is under revision of the UP2030 consortium

until 20 September 2025 in order to make sure that the learnings from the project are reflected appropriately, to be completed by the end of the project).

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 - The Transformative Governance Framework
- ❖ Section 3 – The Process of Operationalising and Testing the Framework
 - Questionnaire
 - Workshop with Budapest on Heat Management Governance
 - Advising Cities on the Governance Aspects on the Upscaling
- ❖ Section 4 – Recommendations on Improving Governance
 - Overall structure
 - Practice-Oriented Next Steps, including Showcasing related UP2030 work

1.3 Section 5 -

The recommendations are supported by practical hints to help practitioners make the first steps on improving the transformative governance dimensions that scored lower on the questionnaire or during a group workshop. Vast material is available online on the topic, and many cities already do advanced work on governance-related streams, often without necessarily thinking about it as governance arrangements. Therefore, these examples and materials that are linked in the recommendations serve a two-fold purpose: clarify quickly what the specific activities (that may already exist) relate to the more abstract recommendation and provide points of fast access to what the immediate first step can be. In other words, the list of examples aims to answer the questions: what does a good governance practice look like and what specific activity/-ies can be undertaken immediately by the user to act on this recommendation?

Therefore, the recommendation section on the platform links to many worksheets and describes existing urban practices very briefly. The material is picked to be common practice and link to well-known sources such as large-scale European efforts (e.g. URBACT, New European Bauhaus, European Urban Initiative). If of interest, additional information or further examples can be found online easily, starting off with these selected links. However, the list of links and examples is intended not to overwhelm the user and should be grasped easily.

Finally, the examples also lead to some of the best practice from UP2030, guiding interested potential users to the instruments developed and approaches tested, and thus helping “popularise” the project’s valuable experiences. Overall, the user should be able to go through the recommendations in about 30 minutes, be able to assess where they stand (what “governance boxes” have they checked already and what structures they can build on) and get an overview of further interesting points to explore.

- ❖ Conclusion
- ❖ Annexes
 - Annex I – Governance analysis questionnaire
 - Annex II – Worksheets for Joint Governance Self-Assessment, e.g. in a Workshop
 - Annex III – Recommendations (Current Version)

2 The Transformative Governance Framework

Many European cities undergo **multiple transformation processes**, as they commit to city-wide, long-term climate neutrality and climate resilience goals (Salvia et al. 2023). While smaller pilot projects have been ongoing over the past years, the challenge now regards their upscaling and mainstreaming. Specific projects so far could be managed by city administrations, often by using external funds and know-how, and establishing individual participation processes. However, city-wide implementation challenges the established governance set-up, including:

- **Cities being governed as a place by city administrations** rather than a system (with shared governance among multiple actors), leading to a concentration of responsibilities and ownership;
- **Siloed working processes and know-how** in many urban institutions, inhibiting an integration and mainstreaming of transformative visions, approaches, and measures;
- **Outdated, inadequate regulatory instruments** (e.g. building laws and standards), hindering innovative solutions to be implemented at large scale; and
- **Limited financial capacities** of city administrations. (Pascual et al. 2022)

Within this UP2030 task, governance is understood as the **structures and processes of decision-making** within a society and the implementation of those decisions. It involves both **formal and informal actors** who are engaged in decision-making. Accordingly, governmental institutions are only one of the actors involved in governance, alongside civil society, private sector, researchers, etc. Urban areas usually present a complex scenario, with a wide range of actors and networks involved in urban governance. According to Baud et al. (2021), “because of its own unique political, economic, social and historical context”, each city has a different decision-making arena that is shaped by institutions and multiple actors – in the following this is referred to as the **governance set-up**. When analysing individual cities’ urban transformation processes, this relational, multi-actor and multi-level understanding of governance is necessary. Based on their unique governance set-up, cities have their individual potentials and individual pathways for driving transformation (Baud et al. 2021). Accordingly, a first step in identifying these potentials and developing suitable pathways is to analyse the status quo of a city’s governance set-up with its **different governance dimensions**.

Figure 2: The five dimensions of transformative governance

The GAF is based on the Governance Assessment Tool by Bressers et al. (2016). It considers five governance dimensions and main assessment questions that were partly adopted and significantly

simplified to develop methodologies for an online questionnaire and a group assessment in a workshop (see Figure 2). Furthermore, a clear scoring system was developed with specific descriptions of each score for each question, to help practitioners assess their status quickly.

Transformation is a broad term used in different disciplines, and it refers to “the notion of **systemic, essential, and radical change**” (Elmqvist et al. 2018). Since the UP2030 project task is to support cities in achieving the EU climate neutrality targets and strengthening their resilience to climate change while ensuring a just transition and increasing liveability, the transformation processes are addressing the changes in this field.

The “**what**” of the transformation is effective climate action (mitigation of emissions, adaptation and just transition). For the “**how**”, different scientific publications (Hölscher et al. (2020), Visseren-Hamekers et al. (2021), Bressers et al. (2016)) were analysed to examine what quality criteria classify processes as “transformative”. In summary, the following six characteristics of transformative governance emerge:

- **Integrative:** bringing together different perspectives and interests while breaking down silos and fostering collaboration across different sectors and departments.
- **Inclusive:** ensuring that all relevant stakeholders, including marginalised groups, have a voice and representation in decision-making processes.
- **Adaptive:** responding and adjusting to changing circumstances, uncertainties, and feedback over time.
- **Pluralist:** recognising and accepting diverse values, beliefs, and ideologies within governance frameworks to foster a more tolerant and democratic society.
- **Long-term:** considering the future implications and sustainability of decisions rather than focusing solely on short-term gains.
- **Intensive (effective, sufficient):** dedication of significant resources, effort, and attention to governance processes to ensure their effectiveness and adequacy in achieving desired outcomes.

These dimensions and characteristics of transformative governance informed the questions and aspects for the self-assessment materials that are described in the next section.

3 Operationalising and Testing the Framework

3.1 Background

In the context of the UP2030 project, transformative governance refers to the norms, institutions, and processes used by cities to make and implement decisions on climate neutrality, resilience, justice, and liveability. The GAF, developed based on Bressers et al. (2016), supports cities in analysing what governance arrangements they need to accelerate and solidify their transformation efforts. The framework operationalises the complex concept of governance, making it more meaningful and relevant to transformation practitioners.

The framework breaks down “transformative governance” into five dimensions: i) goals & perspectives, ii) strategies & instruments, iii) levels & scales, iv) actors & networks, and v) resources & responsibilities (see Section 2). For each of these dimensions, it offers a series of questions for cities to self-assess their status. As also suggested by Bressers et al. (2016), this assessment can be done individually as an online questionnaire or through a workshop with the actors of city’s choice (e.g. internal municipal actors, external stakeholders). The framework offers a list of concise recommendations on how to strengthen the governance structures for transformation, supported by best practice examples and useful material. Several recommendations are particularly relevant for each of the dimensions, so the user can choose to focus on selected dimensions. The recommendations can also be used as a quick checklist to see which aspects are covered better and which actions might still be useful to ramp up the governance arrangements in a particular transformation area.

The UP2030 project used the framework to analyse the governance aspects to upscale the city pilots, supporting continuity and helping produce a lasting impact within the actor and policy landscape of the respective city.

3.2 Analysis of Governance Set-Up via Questionnaire

The [questionnaire](#) (see the complete version in Annex I – Governance analysis questionnaire) is designed to help municipal practitioners assess their governance arrangements for a specific transformative task or a transformation action area they are working on. Based on existing research, it breaks down the concept of transformative governance into five dimensions. For each dimension, several questions need to be answered, most of them by selecting a scoring option of 0 to 4, with zero being the lower scale. There are few questions where the user is asked to fill out an open text field. These questions are not mandatory. Rather, they are a basis for answering the scoring questions that follow (and support structured thinking about the respective issues).

The questionnaire relies entirely on the self-assessment and knowledge of the users. A corresponding workshop methodology is available to conduct this assessment as a group with relevant parts of the city administration and/or with relevant external stakeholders (see Annex II – Worksheets for Joint Governance Self-Assessment, e.g. in a Workshop), which would help expand the knowledge base for the assessment and can be a great first step to bolster transformative governance.

Before starting the questionnaire, the user is asked to define the transformative action area or task they are facing as clearly as possible. The scope of the task can vary from general (e.g. “establishing effective heat management for the city until 2030 in face of climate change”) to specific (e.g. “greening a square”, “ensuring the application of the new retrofitting guideline document within a year”). During the assessment, the user can adjust the scope of the task. Figure 3 show the current view of the questionnaire on the service platform, including the task definition field and the first question with the different scoring options that the user can select.

Governance Tool

0. Task definition

Please phrase the transformative action area or task for which you would like to assess the governance arrangements as precisely as possible, indicating the thematic and territorial scope, and the timeframe of the task.

1. Goals & Perspectives

1.1. Are the goals and objectives regarding your action area / task well-developed? ?

- None
Goals for the area of action do not exist or are unclear, so no meaningful action is possible
- Initial
Some goals exist but are defined poorly. The goals are not clear, or it is not clear how to go about achieving them. Action is stalled.
- Basic
Some goals and objectives are set and SMART, but it is not a comprehensive picture. This enables action that meets basic standards.
- Good
Many goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively in many aspects.
- Advanced
Most goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively.

1.2. Does current political action take a comprehensive perspective your action area / task? ?

Figure 3: Screenshot current view of the governance questionnaire on the service platform, work in progress

Figure 4 shows how the scoring results across the different dimensions will be displayed: as an overview in a spiderweb diagram, as well as with individual question scores for every dimension in pillar diagrams.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the current view of the results of the governance questionnaire, work in progress

3.3 Budapest Workshop

Following expert advice, adelphi initiated collaborations with UP2030 cities interested in co-developing the GAF and the accompanying material. The city of Budapest focused on urban heat management, as part of the transformation field “climate-resilient urban development”, as the city plans to intensify their work in this area. The project team reviewed policy documents provided by Budapest and designed a workshop methodology to analyse the existing governance arrangements, based on the [first deliverable](#) “D5.1 — Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 1”.

The workshop methodology essentially transfers the questionnaire structure into a worksheet template for every dimension that can be filled out as a group, with internal units of city administration and/or external stakeholders, depending on the information needs, process stage and commitment of the stakeholders. These structures of the worksheets for the group are available in Annex II for all five dimensions. These can be either downloaded on the governance framework page of the service platform or easily recreated on flipcharts or pinboards by prospective users (see examples from Budapest) to guide the discussion. For the first step of such a workshop, we recommend conducting an exercise in defining the problem (e.g. problem tree) and visioning on possible solutions. In the online questionnaire for individual self-assessment this is reflected by the open question 0 (see Annex I). For this, the recommendations included methodology pointers under the theory of change section.

The workshop conducted on 12-13 June 2024 with the city of Budapest started with the problem and solution tree exercise on heat management. It then mapped out the five dimensions of transformative governance for this action area, demonstrating that D5.1 was helpful to systematically analyse specific cases. The project team provided a summary presentation of results and recommendations to Budapest. Representatives of different relevant departments of the city of Budapest (incl. climate, water, greening) as well as key stakeholders such as the transportation company and research institutions were present to provide their insights. Figure 5 provides an impression of the results of the discussions in Budapest for different dimensions. For detailed worksheets that were used, please consult Annex II.

There were discussions with Belfast to run a similar workshop, but within timeframe of the project, this did not materialise due to resources constraints for the Pilot Cities in the final phase of the project. However, the framework was used in individual city “coaching sessions” on the governance aspect of upscaling (section 3.4).

Figure 5: Pin Boards with the Governance Discussion in Budapest

3.4 Coaching meetings with Pilot Cities in the upscaling phase

The GAF and the accompanying recommendations were developed as a generalised guide for cities to assess – in a structured way – their governance arrangements for an area or task they are currently working on. This helps understand the actors, institutions, and policy set-up in which the desired actions are taking place and identify strengths and weaknesses for a given transformative endeavour. In the upscaling phase, cities were offered the framework to dive deeper into the governance needs

for the prototype implementation, as well as to understand the possibilities for a broader transformation it can trigger – e.g. in other places or for other actors.

City practitioners can assess five governance dimensions with specific questions and/or directly recur to 11 general recommendations to strengthen governance arrangements, each of which pertain to some of the dimensions. This way, one can choose to prioritise some, based on the dimension they would like to strengthen particularly. The recommendations can also be used as a checklist to see what governance aspects are being tackled and what need can be addressed more.

For the upscaling phase, specifically, the Pilot Cities and adelphi followed the steps below:

- Specify the task to focus on in the upscaling phase.
- Conduct a brief assessment of governance arrangements across the five dimensions.
- Use the governance recommendations as a checklist to identify steps that have been taken already, are underway or planned as well as possible future needs.
- Identify governance aspects to focus on within the Learning and Action Alliance (LAA) workshop, if any – based on possible needs identified.

The envisioned results to support the upscaling phase were:

- Clear vision of the upscaling ambition and tasks.
- Understanding of governance-related strengths and needs.
- Identification of the most relevant next steps to build transformative governance around the prototype and specific elements for the mandatory LAA upscaling workshop to explore this.

This was done in individual “governance coaching meetings” with the Pilot Cities. The meetings rendered individual results that were documented on a MIRO board for the cities to use in the upscaling work. Some cities already had a very advanced vision of the upscaling and the necessary governance arrangements, while others took away initial thoughts on how to integrate this aspect into the future use of their prototype and what specific exercise to go through with their LAAs. The results of these meetings also informed the templates provided to the cities to conduct and document their upscaling activities/plans and to create their transferability packages, led by ICLEI.

4 Recommendations

4.1 The overall structure

A concise list of 11 recommendations helps address all the dimensions of transformative governance to keep the framework actionable and easily accessible, an overview of these recommendations can be seen in Table 1 (see Annex III for the full text). The table below reflects the relevance of each recommendation for different dimensions (if any). This can be used as a checklist for effective governance of transformation and as selected ideas depending on where the gaps are greatest. On the [service platform](#), this is also linked to the UP2030 tools and best practices from pilots that are publicly available, thus promoting the results of the project.

Table 1: The overview of the 11 recommendations for transformative governance, as they related to its dimensions (see section 2).

	Goals & Perspectives	Actors & Networks	Levels & Scales	Strategies & Instruments	Resources & Responsibilities
1	Develop a Theory of Change			Develop a Theory of Change	
2	Adopt a 360 Degree View		Adopt a 360 Degree View		
3	Look into the Future			Look into the Future	
4	Identify Actors and Use Networks	Identify Actors and Use Networks	Identify Actors and Use Networks	Identify Actors and Use Networks	
5	Cater to Vulnerable and Under-Represented Groups	Cater to Vulnerable and Under-Represented Groups			
6		Involve the Private Sector			Involve the Private Sector
7			Promote Productive Multi-Level Exchange		
8				Work on a Smart Instrument Mix	
9				Encourage Innovation	
10					Clarify and Enable Roles and Responsibilities
11					Strive for an Adequate Budget

On the [service platform](#), the recommendations are available as a separate page, with best practices and methodology tips to use (see section 4.2). Based on the questionnaire, only the relevant are highlighted (as shown in Table 1), so the user can start with the most immediate entry points and is not overwhelmed by all the possibilities for action. When interpreting the questionnaire results, several rules are applied to ensure that recommendations are tailored and actionable. If the average

score of the answers to the questions for a particular dimension falls below 2 (please see Annex I for the scoring definitions for each question), the recommendations relevant to that dimension are highlighted. In cases where four or five dimensions receive scores below 2, only the three lowest-scoring dimensions are highlighted, ensuring that no more than three dimensions are emphasised at any one time.

Once the user completes the questionnaire, they will see the full list of recommended activities, with the most pertinent ones highlighted in bold, with the following explanation: “Thanks for assessing the governance landscape for your action area or task! If you would like to work on advancing some of the dimensions of transformative governance, our list of eleven recommended activities might be helpful. Based on your results, you could start with the activities highlighted below.” The phrase “list of recommended activities” will be linked to the platform editorial page with all the recommendations.

4.2 Implementation help with best practices and methodologies

The recommendations are supported by practical hints to help practitioners make the first steps on improving the transformative governance dimensions that scored lower on the questionnaire or during a group workshop. Vast material is available online on the topic, and many cities already do advanced work on governance-related streams, often without necessarily thinking about it as governance arrangements. Therefore, these examples and materials that are linked in the recommendations serve a two-fold purpose: clarify quickly what the specific activities (that may already exist) relate to the more abstract recommendation and provide points of fast access to what the immediate first step can be. In other words, the list of examples aims to answer the questions: what does a good governance practice look like and what specific activity/-ies can be undertaken immediately by the user to act on this recommendation?

Therefore, the recommendation section on the platform links to many worksheets and describes existing urban practices very briefly. The material is picked to be common practice and link to well-known sources such as large-scale European efforts (e.g. URBACT, New European Bauhaus, European Urban Initiative). If of interest, additional information or further examples can be found online easily, starting off with these selected links. However, the list of links and examples is intended not to overwhelm the user and should be grasped easily.

Finally, the examples also lead to some of the best practice from UP2030, guiding interested potential users to the instruments developed and approaches tested, and thus helping “popularise” the project’s valuable experiences. Overall, the user should be able to go through the recommendations in about 30 minutes, be able to assess where they stand (what “governance boxes” have they checked already and what structures they can build on) and get an overview of further interesting points to explore.

5 Conclusion

The UP2030 project support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging urban planning and design. The GAF, as part of the UP2030 UP-scaling phase, aims to break down the complexity of transformative governance for city practitioners to help establish structures that enable effective action. It recognizes the need for practical guidance to help cities achieve climate neutrality, justice, and resilience through effective governance. The “business as usual” of pilot initiatives managed by one municipal department can hinder wide implementation by overloading urban practitioners and creating conflicts within the city administrations as well as with other stakeholders. This framework promotes integrative action, overcoming usual barriers and silos, and multilevel collaboration to facilitate transformative governance fit for the tasks cities face.

During the conceptualisation phase of the framework, the feedback from an expert panel led to the efforts of making it as practical as possible, by creating an interactive tool and a workshop methodology. It has also profited greatly from engaging with the Pilot Cities, both during the framework development (testing workshop with Budapest) and in the upscaling phase of UP2030, which included meetings with all the cities to discuss the governance arrangements for upscaling their pilots.

Having tested this approach with practitioners, the team can provide an easy-to-use online resource that can be maintained beyond the UP2030 project as part of the service platform. The questionnaire, the workshop methodology and the recommendations will be available for download. This material was also created to be transferable to subsequent urban sustainable development projects involving practitioners. If any content updates emerge from this, the material can be updated on the service platform, as the partners involved aim to maintain the platform after UP2030 ends. The respective Memorandum of Understanding is being developed. The content and examples linked in the recommendations were chosen as sources that are likely to persist for a long time, as they are linked to large-scale European efforts (e.g. URBACT, New European Bauhaus, European Urban Initiative) and present methodological approaches that are easily found online. Most importantly, the partners involved in creating the service platform are currently exploring possibilities to connect this resource to the NetZeroCities platform and the Smart Cities Marketplace. This will help ensure the use of the service platform beyond the end of UP2030.

The development of the governance framework has been aligned with the progress on visioning and pathway development, and it has been an integral part of the upscaling phase led by ICLEI. The recommendations include the relevant and publicly available UP2030 experiences as practical guidance for cities who would like to work on transformative governance in the future.

Until the end of the UP2030 project in December 2025, the following steps are planned: 1) gathering input from the consortium and members of the expert panel until 20 September to make sure the recommendations are complete; 2) finalisation of the recommendations and all the GAF-related text and downloads for the service platform until 20 October; 3) finalisation of the online questionnaire tool and a short tutorial video of how to use it for the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC) until 30 November.

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Annexes

Annex I – Governance analysis questionnaire

0. Task definition

Please phrase the transformative action area or task for which you would like to assess the governance arrangements as precisely as possible, indicating the thematic and territorial scope, and the timeframe of the task.

1. Goals & Perspectives

1.1. Are the goals and objectives regarding your action area / task well-developed?

Setting the goals appropriately is of key importance for success: they need to be defined clearly and have specific objectives that, in turn, have clear contents, sequencing and ways to measure progress. The acronym often used is SMART – Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound. In other words, it is clear how to proceed to achieve the goals and when they have been achieved.

0 – None: Goals for the area of action do not exist or are unclear, so no meaningful action is possible.

1 – Initial: Some goals exist but are defined poorly. The goals are not clear, or it is not clear how to go about achieving them. Action is stalled.

2 – Basic: Some goals and objectives are set and SMART, but it is not a comprehensive picture. This enables action that meets basic standards.

3 – Good: Many goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively in many aspects.

4 – Advanced: Most goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively.

1.2. Does current political action take a comprehensive perspective your action area / task?

Urban development tasks usually need to be viewed from different perspectives (technical, social, economic, ecologic), e.g. through a broad assessment of socio-economic costs and benefits and including multiple disciplines. It can mean thinking about links to different sectors, e.g. social dynamics, built environment, mobility flows, health services, ecosystems.

0 – None: The action area / task is only seen from one perspective, or the question of different components and perspectives has never been considered.

1 – Initial: There is some understanding of different perspectives of the task / action area, but no explicit analysis or assessment of these perspectives.

2 – Basic: There some explicit consideration of different perspectives of the action area / task, e.g. with one assessment instrument or in a document or in a working process between different actors.

3 – Good: There explicit consideration of different perspectives of the action area / task, through an effective instrument or process that has been established specifically to achieve this.

4 – Advanced: There is an elaborate process or instrument established to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the task in question, considering a wide array of perspectives on a permanent basis.

1.3. Does setting the goals and objectives include an appropriate procedure to consider different groups of the population?

Public sector action impacts people differently depending on their age, educational background, gender, household type, income level, place of residence, physical fitness etc. These impacts should be considered and assessed to make sure people benefit in an equitable way. This includes accessibility issues and specific consideration of population groups especially vulnerable to the issue in question.

0 - None: Different population groups are not at all a topic when goals and objectives are set.

1 – Initial: Different population groups are mentioned when goals and objectives for the action area / task are set.

2 – Basic: Implications for the different population are discussed in some detail when goals and objectives for the action area / task are set.

3 – Good: Implications for the different population are discussed substantially when goals and objectives for the action area / task are set; there is a specific procedure or process for this (e.g. assessment).

4 – Advanced: Implications for the different population groups are discussed profoundly when goals and objectives for the action area / task are set, and this discussion continues when the goal achievement is monitored.

1.4. Do the goals and objectives for your action area / task account sufficiently for the future, including possible “unknowns”?

The goals, even for the short and medium term, are not set with the view of the immediate future but keep circumstances in mind that might arise later, for instance, by being aligned with a longer-term strategy or by having been set in view of different scenarios. The question is asked what implications the goals and objectives might have for the long term (lock-ins, path dependencies etc.).

Please rate your status:

0 - None: Possible future developments are not at all considered in current goals.

1 – Initial: Possible future developments are mentioned in current documents that set out goals, but there is no specific indication of what this means for current action.

2 – Basic: Possible future developments are mentioned in current documents that set out goals, and there is some indication of what this means for current action.

3 – Good: Possible future developments are mentioned in current documents that set out goals, and it is sufficiently clear what this means for current action in the area.

4 – Advanced: Possible future developments are integrated specifically in current goals and objectives, and there are specific ways of adapting goals and objectives and dealing with uncertainty.

1.5. Do stakeholders share the goals and objectives for your action area / task (civil society, local businesses, etc.)?

Municipal goals and actions are affected by what many other actors do. It benefits the task in question greatly, if the goals of these actors are aligned with those of the municipality, allowing for cooperation and synergies between measures.

Please rate your status:

0 - None: There is no match with or no consideration/knowledge of stakeholders' goals.

1 – Initial: In some respects, the goals are shared by stakeholders, but it is mostly coincidental and offers no significant potential for cooperation or synergies yet.

2 – Basic: In several aspects, the goals are shared by stakeholders, which offers some potential for cooperation or synergies.

3 – Good: In many aspects, the goals are shared by stakeholders, which offers good potential for cooperation or synergies.

4 –Advanced: In most aspects, the goals are shared by other stakeholders, which offers excellent potential for cooperation or synergies.

2. Strategies & Instruments

2.1. Please list existing policy instruments relevant for your action area / task.

Most policy issues are complex and multi-dimensional, and a mix of different instruments may be best suited to deal with them effectively. The choice of the instruments might vary for different governance contexts. Possible policy instrument types are:

Informational: These instruments disseminate information and promote certain behaviours or practices (e.g. public awareness campaigns, education programs, and endorsements by actors).

Economic: Financial or economic instruments include mechanisms such as subsidies, grants, taxes, and incentives designed to influence economic behaviour.

Legal: Legal instruments are laws and regulations, requiring compliance with specific rules and standards, often backed by penalties for non-compliance.

Co-operative: These instruments build upon collaboration between various stakeholders, including governments, private sector entities, non-profits, and communities; emphasis on resource sharing, leveraging the strengths and capabilities of each partner, synergies and collective impact.

Strategic: Long-term planning and comprehensive strategies to address complex issues; a coherent and coordinated framework for achieving policy objectives over time.

(Open question text field)

2.2. Is the present mix of (regulatory, strategic, economic, co-operative and informational) instruments appropriate for your action area/task?

Successful municipal action needs a balanced and effective mix of different types of instruments to address the issue in question from different sides and with a combination of levers. This does not mean that all types of instruments need to be used; rather, that the instrument mix works well to tackle the envisioned task.

0 – None: Most required instrument types are lacking. Ineffective mix fails to address diverse needs.

1 – Initial: Instruments of some types exist, but it is unclear if this allows effective action.

2 – Basic: Instruments of several types exist, allowing to tackle several dimensions of the action area / task.

3 – Good: A diverse instrument mix allows to tackle the different aspects of the action area / task well.

4 – Advanced: A diverse and well-developed instrument mix covers most aspects of the action area / task, and the instruments are complementary.

2.3. Do existing instruments allow to plan in the long term, adapt to change and deal with uncertainties?

As urban development often deals with long-term issues and infrastructure, planning should account for how the decisions of today may impact the upcoming years. This includes the possibility to adapt to change appropriately and having an approach for circumstances that cannot be foreseen today. Ideally, the instrument mix answers the question of what should be done if something unknown or unexpected emerges and how to best prepare for this.

0 - None: The instruments are rigid, do not support long-term planning and do not adapt to changes or uncertainties.

1 - Initial: Limited long-term planning and flexibility are possible, while the instruments are rather rigid and do not account for uncertainties explicitly.

2 - Basic: Some support for long-term planning exists. The instruments can handle some uncertainties but are not highly flexible.

3 - Good: The instruments support long-term planning and are adaptable. They handle uncertainties reasonably well.

4 - Advanced: The instruments support long-term planning and are highly adaptable. They have in-built mechanisms to manage uncertainties.

2.4. Do existing instruments promote innovation for transformative change?

Innovation for positive transformations at scale requires conducive conditions and incentives. The policy instrument mix should effectively promote this, encouraging new ideas, ways of collaboration, and technologies that can drive substantial change.

0 – None: Innovation is not promoted by existing instruments.

1 – Initial: Existing instruments have a few single levers to promote innovation for transformative change or allow this to happen on occasion.

2 – Basic: Existing instruments include some levers to promote innovation for transformative change.

3 – Good: Existing instruments reflect explicitly on the question of promoting innovation for transformative change and include several effective levers to do so.

4 – Advanced: Promoting innovation for transformative change is an integral part and an explicit dimension of the existing instrument mix.

2.5. Please list relevant instruments by non-public actors for the action area / task.

Actors outside of public authorities (e.g. business, NGOs, community organizations, etc.) use their own strategies, tools, and resources to act on urban development questions. These can be funding programs, technological solutions, collaborative networks or partnerships, capacity-building programs, certification standards, data analytics tools, and community engagement strategies.

(Open question text field)

2.6. Do the instruments of non-public actors play a meaningful role in the area in question, allowing to use synergies and find effective solutions?

It is beneficial to scope the relevant instruments and strategies employed by non-public entities, to understand whether these contribute meaningfully to the objectives of the public sector and to effective solutions for your action area / task.

0 – None: Strategies and instruments outside the public sector have no impact or are unknown.

1 – Initial: Strategies and instruments outside the public sector contribute marginally. Synergies with the public sector action are limited, and effective solutions are identified and implemented rarely.

2 – Basic: Strategies and instruments outside the public sector have some (known) impact. Synergies with the public sector action are observed but are not fully leveraged, and effective solutions are identified and implemented on occasion.

3 – Good: Strategies and instruments outside the public sector have a significant (known) impact. Synergies with the public sector action are used, and effective solutions are implemented regularly.

4 – Advanced: Strategies and instruments outside the public sector are key. Synergies with the public sector action are extensive, resulting in highly collaborative and integrated approaches. Effective solutions are consistently identified and implemented, leading to significant achievements.

3. Actors & Networks

3.1. Please list the actors outside the city administration that are relevant for the area in question and identify the most important ones.

Besides the responsible departments in the city administration, many other actors “hold stakes” in the action area or task and therefore need to be involved to achieve sound results. These actors come from different areas, including other public institutions, private sector, e.g. businesses and financial institutions, civil society, media, and academia. There are different levels of proximity to the actors implementing the task – core stakeholders who actively contribute; second-level stakeholders to consult; or broader groups of stakeholders to keep informed.

(Open question text field)

3.2. For the main actors, please rate if an appropriate mode of interaction exists with regard the area in question.

Depending on the actor and process phase, appropriate mode of interaction can vary: active participation in decision-making where their input has a tangible impact on outcomes, consultation on measures, information exchange etc. These actors also require access to relevant information, resources, and opportunities to collaborate effectively, so that their contributions are valued and utilised.

0 – None: No interaction modes exist that allow to involve the stakeholders in an appropriate manner. Their potential roles are unclear, and there is no infrastructure for them to get involved.

1 – Initial: Limited interaction modes exist to involve the stakeholders in an appropriate manner. Their involvement is sporadic, with ad-hoc roles and support to it.

2 – Basic: Some interaction modes exist to involve the stakeholders in a meaningful manner. There are occasional opportunities for and support to this, but they are not consistent.

3 – Good: Adequate interaction modes exist to involve the stakeholders in a meaningful manner, and the roles are clear. There are regular opportunities for involvement.

4 – Advanced: Comprehensive and effective interaction modes exist to involve the stakeholders in a meaningful manner. The actors are consistently involved on numerous opportunities with clear roles.

3.3. Is the private sector involved and takes active roles in the area in question?

Private sector resources are very helpful and often needed for successful urban development, so it is important to have businesses, associations and financial sector on board. This can be in form of private public partnerships (PPPs) or looser modes of collaboration, e.g. ensuring their perspectives are well-understood and entry points for collaboration are clear.

0 - None: There is no meaningful interaction with the private sector and their perspectives are unclear.

1 – Initial: Some involvement of the private sector happens, but it is scattered and not systematic.

2 – Basic: Involvement of the private sector happens on several occasions, and this provides some synergies and support for the action area.

3 – Good: Involvement of the private sector happens on many occasions, and this provides constant synergies and support for the action area.

4 – Advanced: Involvement of the private sector is steady and strategic, which provides substantial synergies and support for the action area.

3.4. Please list vulnerable as well as under-represented groups from the perspective of your action area / task.

Some groups can be much more affected by challenge in question than others, either because they have high vulnerability to the issue (vulnerable groups, such as children, the elderly, people with disabilities, low-income populations) or because their needs are often not appropriately reflected in policies and measures (under-represented groups, such as the urban poor, ethnic minorities, women, persons with disabilities, migrants, and refugees).

(Open question text field)

3.5. For the vulnerable and under-represented groups, please indicate if there is an effective mode of including their needs and perspectives in decision-making process with regard to your action area / task.

For effective municipal action, it is important to integrate the needs and perspectives of vulnerable and under-represented groups, ensuring people benefit from transformation equally and no risks are unintentionally exacerbated. Such groups are often affected more and/or are not necessarily reached by public action, if not considered specifically in its design.

0 – None: There are no mechanisms in place to include the needs and perspectives of this group. No documentation or evidence of considers these groups in decision making or planning.

1 – Initial: Perspectives of these groups are acknowledged only in a general manner, based on statistical data or demographics without direct engagement. Some policy documents mention these groups, but there is no involvement in the decision-making process.

2 – Basic: Some efforts are made to consider the perspectives of these groups, e.g. sporadic surveys or basic consultations. There is some involvement in the decision-making process, but not in a systematic way or rather in later phases.

3 – Good: There are established procedures for including these groups in the decision-making process, e.g. regular consultations, focus groups, or public forums. The feedback is considered in planning and policymaking, but their influence on final decisions may be limited.

4 – Advanced: Continuous and proactive engagement ensures that the needs and perspectives of these groups are integrated into the city's governance and planning processes. There are consistent mechanisms for including them in all stages of policymaking and planning. They are actively involved in decision-making bodies and have a substantial role in shaping public action.

3.6. Do networks exist and are utilised effectively where stakeholders work with the city on the area in question?

Municipal action can benefit greatly from cooperation in networks with other cities, research, civil society or other actors (including using knowledge, resources, best practices from other stakeholders/cities/institutions).

0 – Not at all: There is no noteworthy collaboration in networks.

1 – Initial: Networks exist, but are used only on single occasions, with no substantial support.

2 – Basic: Networks exists and are used on several occasions for meaningful support.

3 – Good: Good networks exist and often provide meaningful support.

4 –Advanced: Good networks of different kinds exist and provide steady, meaningful support.

4. Levels & Scales

4.1. Please list the different political levels relevant your action area / task, if possible, indicating roughly where the legislative and executive competences lie.

The relevant levels that can be involved are local (e.g. city district), subnational (city, region), national, EU or international, while the competence to set laws and other regulations can be distributed differently, depending on the action area / task.

(Open question text field)

4.2. Are existing rules and regulations on relevant political levels well-structured and aligned for effective action on the tasks in question?

The different political levels should ideally interact in an effective way, including: the political competencies are sufficient for the actors who need to act; the levels are complementary, so there are no major conflicting or unclear competencies and no major gaps (where action is needed, but no level acts). Policies and actions at higher political levels sufficiently address challenges at the local level.

0 – None: Rules, regulations and competences on different levels are scattered and not at all aligned. No effective action is possible.

1 – Initial: On single aspects, rules, regulation and competences are aligned, but this is largely insufficient for effective action.

2 – Basic: In some aspects, rules, regulation and competences are aligned and well-structured, and this allows some effective action, while challenges arise regularly.

3 – Good: In many aspects, rules, regulation and competences are aligned and well-structured, and this supports effective action, even though challenges arise occasionally.

4 – Advanced: Rules, regulation and competences are aligned and well-structured, and this enables action, with no major gaps or challenges.

4.3. Are appropriate mechanisms in place to ensure sufficient coordination of these political levels?

Different political levels should be able to negotiate governance structures for tackling issues effectively and facilitate a good connection of policies to the reality on the ground. For this, they should have a way to communicate with each other. Ideally, lower governance levels can present their needs and challenges and receive sufficient information and support. In turn, higher levels succeed in receiving information from lower levels and achieving effective policy implementation.

0 – None: No channels of communication and coordination exist between political levels.

1 – Initial: There are limited channels of communication. Some coordination mechanisms exist, but are mostly insufficient.

2 – Basic: Some channels of communication and coordination structures exist. Helpful coordination takes place on some issues.

3 – Good: Good channels of communication and coordination structures exist. Helpful coordination takes place on many issues.

4 – Advanced: Channels of communication and coordination structures work very well. Helpful coordination takes place on most issues.

4.4. Please list the different sectors involved in the area in question and the mechanisms bring them together.

For most municipal tasks, different units of public administration need to interact with each other, connecting sectors, albeit separate administration entities or different departments within one entity.

(Open question text field)

4.5. Do the relevant sectors and units collaborate in an appropriate way, regularly and with consistent participation?

Ideally, an interaction between different units of administration is possible that is needed in the specific situation, and every sector is willing and able to participate. Depending on the collaboration needs, this can range from active collaboration to consultation and making knowledge available to keeping the relevant departments informed.

0 – None: There is no meaningful interaction between relevant sectors/units.

1 – Initial: On some occasions, there is interaction between relevant sectors/units, but is mostly not sufficient for appropriate collaboration.

2 – Basic: On several occasions, there is interaction between relevant sectors/units, and it is sometimes sufficient for appropriate collaboration.

3 – Good: On many occasions, there is interaction between relevant sectors/units, and it is often sufficient for appropriate collaboration.

4 – Advanced: On most occasions, there is interaction between relevant sectors/units, and it is almost always sufficient for appropriate collaboration.

5. Resources & Responsibilities

5.1. Are the roles and responsibilities for your action area / task clearly and appropriately distributed?

For successful action, roles and responsibilities should be allocated in a way that supports effective collaboration and task completion, avoiding overlaps or gaps, while each actor should have clarity on the task distribution and their specific duties.

0 – None: There is no clarity or documentation on roles and responsibilities, so overlaps and gaps in tasks are prevalent.

1 – Initial: There is some information and minimal documentation on roles and responsibilities. Gaps, overlaps and ambiguities are frequent.

2 – Basic: Most roles and responsibilities are defined and documented, but some ambiguities as well as gaps and overlaps remain. Overall, the structure is functional.

3 – Good: Roles and responsibilities are defined clearly and documented adequately, with only occasional gaps or overlaps. The structure works well in most situations.

4 – Advanced: Roles and responsibilities are defined clearly, and sufficient documentation is accessible to everyone involved. Gaps or overlaps are an exception. The structure works smoothly, enabling actors to deal with challenging situations and to adapt workflows to new situations.

5.2. Are the main actors tasked with responsibilities well-equipped to take them on (e.g. time, skills, organisational support, technology/tools)?

A clear and functional distribution of roles and responsibilities is an important step. At the same time, actors have the resources to fulfil their roles. This might not only require time, knowledge and skill, but also support structures (e.g. legal advice) or specific technologies. (Please note that budgetary resources are covered under a separate question.)

0 – None: The limited resource availability hinders task performance.

1 – Initial: The resources for the assigned tasks are available only sporadically, and these can only be performed if respective actors are highly motivated and at the expense of other tasks.

2 - Basic: Some, yet insufficient resources are available, so that the tasks can be performed to a minimal standard.

3 - Good: Sufficient resources are available most of the time, so that the tasks can be performed well and constantly, if no extraordinary circumstances or extra requirements arise.

4 - Advanced: Sufficient resources are available, so that the tasks can be performed well and constantly. Additionally, resource buffers exist for extraordinary circumstances or extra requirements, and measures exist to expand the resources for the future (capacity building, seeking new collaboration avenues).

5.3. Please describe the budget lines / financial resources available by the city administration for the area in question.

Please list the financial resources that the city administration has allocated or can access for the tasks in question. This helps understand the funding structure and the public financial commitment to support these actions.

(Open question text field)

5.4. Is sufficient budget allocated to the activities and/or units involved in your action area / task?

The activities and units involved in the specified action area / task require sufficient financial resources.

0 – None: No budget is allocated, so tasks cannot be performed due to lack of funds.

1 – Initial: Budget allocation is insufficient and significantly limits performance, but some tasks can proceed. Financial planning and review mechanisms are emerging.

2 – Basic: Budget allocation allows a basic level of task performance, and some financial planning and review mechanisms exist.

3 – Good: Budget allocation is sufficient for all major tasks, and occasional budget issues are manageable. There are effective financial planning and review mechanisms.

4 – Advanced: Budget allocation allows performing current tasks well and expanding tasks for the future, with robust financial planning and review mechanisms in place.

5.5. Are there workable procedures in place to acquire additional resources if needed (incl. financial, human, knowledge)?

Additionally to the present budget availability, it is important to have avenues of acquiring future funds. Even if budget is limited now, potentially available sources can make a difference (e.g. EU funds), depending on how easy it is for the responsible actors to access them.

0 - None: No procedures or knowledge exist for acquiring additional resources, and there is no contingency planning.

1 - Initial: Some information and ideas exist for acquiring additional resources, but this is not available to everyone involved and requires a lot of effort. There is no contingency planning.

2 - Basic: Procedures and knowledge on how to acquire resources are available to responsible actors, but there are regular delays and difficulties. Contingency planning happens on occasion.

3 - Good: Effective procedures are in place for acquiring resources, and this generally happens in a timely manner. Contingency planning is established.

4 - Advanced: There are highly effective and efficient procedures for acquiring resources with institutionalised knowledge on the matter. Resources are always acquired swiftly and without significant issues. There is effective contingency planning.

5.6. Is there sufficient allocation of financial and human resources to the action area / task by private actors?

Financial and human resources of the private sector can be an important building block to advancing urban change. Examples are real estate developers in the area investing in green building projects, corporations funding urban green spaces, and private investors supporting sustainable infrastructure initiatives or innovations.

0 - None: No financial/ human resources are allocated, so tasks cannot be performed.

1 - Initial: Resource allocation is insufficient and significantly limits task performance, but occasional contributions happen.

2 - Basic: Resource allocation allows a basic level of task performance.

3 - Good: Resource allocation is sufficient for all major tasks, and occasional bottlenecks are manageable.

4 - Advanced: Resource allocation allows performing current tasks well and expanding tasks for the future.

Annex II – Worksheets for Joint Governance Self-Assessment, e.g. in a Workshop

The worksheets have been developed to assess the transformative governance dimensions with a group of people and tested in a one-day workshop with the city of Budapest (the afternoon of 12 June and the morning of 13 June 2024). The workshop participants worked on filling out the templates on groups and then shared the results in the plenary. They follow the structure of the self-assessment questionnaire but do not include all its questions as the content has been adapted to a group setting.

Goals & Perspectives

<p>Are the goals and objectives with regard to the issue in question well-developed? (SMART – Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound)</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Does current political action take a comprehensive perspective on the issue in question?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Does setting the goals include an appropriate procedure to consider different groups of the population?</p> <p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Do the goals account sufficiently for the future, including possible “unknowns”?</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Are goals on the issue in question shared by/match with other stakeholders (e.g. civil society, commercial chambers, etc.)?</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>

Strategies & Instruments

<p>Please list relevant instruments and strategies in place. If possible, also think about non-governmental actors who often have their own strategies.</p>	
<p>Is there an appropriate mix of regulatory, strategical, economic, co-operative and informational instruments?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Do these instruments allow to plan in the long term, adapt to change and deal with uncertainties?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Do these instruments promote innovation for transformative change?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>

Actors & Networks

<p>Please list the actors outside the city administration that are relevant for the area in question. Identify the most important ones. Does appropriate mode of interaction with them exist with regard the area in question?</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Is the private sector involved and takes active roles in the area in question?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Is there an effective mode of including the needs and perspectives of the vulnerable and under-represented groups in decision-making processes?</p> <p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Do networks exist and are they utilised effectively where stakeholders work with the city on the area in question?</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>

Levels & Scales

<p>Please list the relevant political levels, indicating roughly where the legislative and executive competences lie.</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Please list the different sectors involved in the area in question and the mechanisms bring them together.</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Are existing political levels well-aligned for effective action? Are appropriate coordination mechanisms in place?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Do the relevant sectors and units collaborate well?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>

Resources & Responsibilities

<p>Are the roles and responsibilities for the issue in question clearly and appropriately distributed?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Are the main actors tasked with responsibilities well-equipped to take them (e.g. time, skills, organisational support, technology/tools)?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Is sufficient budget allocated to the tasks and/or units involved in the issue in question?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	<p>Are there workable procedures in place to acquire additional resources if needed (incl. financial, human, knowledge)?</p>	<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>
<p>Is there sufficient allocation of financial and human resources to the issue in question by private actors?</p>		<p>0 1 2 3 4</p>	

Annex III – Recommendations (Current Version)

The following is the current version of the recommendations. Further input to complete it is being gathered from the consortium by 20 September 2025. The recommendations will be finalized by 20 October 2025. Below to the recommendation text, helpful material (grey), best practices (blue) and experiences and results of UP2030 (green) are provided.

1. **Develop a Theory of Change:** Developing a theory of change makes working on better governance for transformations much easier. It makes your assumptions on how change should happen through the measures that you take explicit: while every project tends to build on implicit ideas of how change would work, discussing this explicitly makes possible gaps and needs visible. These assumptions can be tested and adjusted, enabling learning about what works better or not quite as well.

A theory of change is especially relevant for developing a **vision of change** you are working towards, setting the goals and assessing the strategies and instruments to achieve this. It also helps with identifying the actors and institutional structures that are necessary for change to happen. An explicit theory of change puts a spotlight on the **process** of transformation (who needs to do what and why), understanding what difficulties the current governance landscapes presents and how to work with these. It also makes the uncertainties and questions around the possibilities for change more visible.

Establishing a theory of change essentially involves specifying the vision of your task, translating this into **SMART** (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) **goals** and making this concrete with a set of indicators (on the levels of output and outcome). This allows to map out the process and identify the **specific steps** towards the envisioned goals – ideally in a corresponding visual the team can go back to, track the progress and adjust as needed. This is a good basis to explore the operational context and what the enabling and hindering circumstances might be for each step of the way.

Finally, discussing this **in a team and with stakeholders** already improves the outlook of your efforts by clarifying the understanding of the work, sourcing knowledge and ensuring support to a specific vision.

Helpful material to create a theory of change is available here:

- The [Designing participatory transformative processes for just & climate neutral cities. Workbook for Urban Transition Makers. Vollume II](#) by DRIFT offers a deep dive into transition concepts and support this with tools to implement change. With the Transition Canvas and Action Plan Canvas it provides elaborate templates for practitioners who are enthusiastic about transition processes and seek to make ambitious change happen in their working domains.
- Conducting a visioning exercise can kick-start the work on a theory of change with a group, e.g. with the method of the [Newspaper of Tomorrow](#).
- The URBACT toolkit provides straightforward templates on clarifying how your effort will [create change](#), through describing aims, activities, outputs etc., defining [SMART goals](#) and [indicators](#).
- [Guidebook for the Monitoring & evaluation of ecosystem-based adaptation](#): This Guidebook helps for planners and practitioners better understand the outcomes and impacts of on-the-ground Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EbA) projects. It describes key considerations and components for each step of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) of EbA projects and points to additional tools and methodologies that can be used in specific circumstances.

- The S²Cities initiative created this visual of a [Theory of Change – outlining intended outputs, outcomes, impacts – to map](#) the complex factors influencing urban safety, engaging stakeholders such as youth, local authorities, civil society and the private sector.

2. **Adopt a 360 Degree View on the Task:** Urban planning is inherently interconnected, making it essential to understand how your action area or task **is linked with various topics and sectors**. Insights and expertise from relevant sectors such as environment, planning, transport, and social affairs, as well as from different governance levels, help to better understand the underlying issues and develop effective solutions, thereby enriching the theory of change. Mapping the relevant areas and identifying where these inputs can be most beneficial at different stages of the process can significantly strengthen your governance approach.

Ensuring that the **methods of involving other units** are both resource-efficient and results-oriented helps sustain collaboration. Approaches may include direct participation, for example cross-departmental workshops, joint planning sessions and working groups as well as consultation through targeted surveys, feedback rounds or departmental interviews, ad hoc exchanges, and requests for input. The choice of method should be purposeful and tailored to the specific stage of the process.

Helpful material to create a comprehensive understanding of the task is available here.

- A simple way of mapping the different dimensions of a problem is a [problem tree](#) exercise – which can be turned into a solution tree in a second step by suggesting [appropriate solutions](#) for the different dimensions of the challenge. Involving a group of diverse professionals and stakeholders can help get a comprehensive view of the issue and avoid blind spots when addressing it. The UP2030 Pilot City [Belfast](#) additionally applied [fuzzy cognitive mapping](#) to include stakeholders' knowledge.
- The [New European Bauhaus](#) embodies a 360-degree approach by bridging science, technology, art, and culture, and fostering collaboration across governance levels including grassroots, local and European actors. It uses co-creation methods to bring together citizens, experts, businesses, and institutions, e.g. Empathy Mapping (p. 29 of [the New European Bauhaus Toolbox](#))

Some best practice examples are:

- The [H2020 RESPONSE](#) project establishes a strategic vision for climate-neutral smart cities by 2050, supporting lighthouse cities like Dijon and Turku and further cities across Europe. RESPONSE exemplifies a 360-degree approach by engaging city governments, research centres, technology providers, and citizens in co-designing solutions that address energy security, affordability, and sustainability - at building, block, and district levels. Its integrated [evaluation framework](#) aims to ensure that actions in energy, mobility, governance, and citizen engagement are monitored collaboratively, to enable all sectors and stakeholders to shape and assess progress together.
 - Leuven implements its Climate Adaptation Plan (2020-2025) through multiple city departments working together (see [case study](#), pp. 14). This means that issues such as greening the city or improving mobility are not handled in isolation but are integrated across various projects and departments. For example, the Green Management Department collaborates with the Mobility Department to ensure that when parking spaces are replaced by green areas, alternative mobility solutions are also implemented.
3. **Look into the Future:** As municipal action often aims at long-lasting structures, it should explicitly consider potential future developments when establishing goals and strategies for change. Testing envisioned measures against **different scenarios** can help ensure that strategies remain effective

in the face of uncertainty and changing circumstances. It can also help you explore how the instruments can be adapted in the face of change.

Specifically, you can assess how the proposed measures and instruments align with existing long-term municipal strategies, regional development plans or sectoral forecasts or engage in scenario development (e.g. through joint scenario planning sessions, structured adaptation frameworks). It is essential to consider [climate scenarios](#) in planning processes and to ensure that particularly long-lasting structures—such as infrastructure, buildings, and broader aspects of urban development like neighbourhood planning and transport concepts—are designed to be climate-proof.

You can discuss **mechanisms to address uncertainties and adapt your strategies**, such as regular reviews of goals and indicators, specific expert bodies that can adjust the measures, flexible budgeting arrangements.

To start “futureproofing” your action some of the following group exercises can be conducted:

- The EU Harmonise project created a workbook for city decision makers that can help understand future changes with their threats and opportunities: [Participatory scenario building - A tool for city planners](#).
- Participatory scenario planning, as described [in this brief report](#) with implementation examples, applies “different methods to identify relevant stakeholders, create a set of scenarios, and explore ways to connect those future visions to the present”.
- You can also use the famous method of [six thinking hats](#) (or by [URBACT](#)) to conduct a creative and engaging workshop to think about different possible development.

- 4. Identify Relevant Actors and Use Networks:** The question of who should be involved is central for effective transformational governance of any municipal endeavour. It is often already managed well, as the municipal level actively collaborates with civil society, social and education organisations, urban professionals/experts/academia and other municipalities on a variety of topics. At the same time, some transformational areas require exploring new collaboration arrangements and consultation modes that are tailored for this specific task.

Possible points to consider, depending on how well-developed your stakeholder collaboration modes are, include:

- Stakeholder **mapping** to identify all the relevant actors in the area in question, grouping them, e.g.
 - Based on sector: governmental actors, civil society, the private sector; based on their influence on your area of work (from veto players to one who might need to be informed only)
 - Explore what **existing networks** can contribute to the achievement of the envisioned transformation.
- **Field analysis** to familiarise yourself with the stakeholders’ activities (programmes, objectives, missions, projects)
 - Seek to **understand the goals, perspectives and needs** of as many local and regional stakeholders as possible and identify common interests, identify where your goals naturally align with other stakeholders to increase buy-in for your goal, collaboration and implementation efficiency;
 - Map the relationship between different stakeholders (formal cooperation, other formal relationship, informal relationship; use symbols to identify positive and challenging relationships)

- Maintain a **regular awareness of tools and initiatives** used by relevant non-public actors, e.g. through annual reviews as part of the stakeholder analysis (to understand ongoing activities and identify opportunities for collaborative approaches).
- **Create and maintain relevant collaboration modes**, identifying suitable interaction formats for specific needs, including:
 - **Choose formats** based on the characteristics of the target groups, engagement objectives and mutual benefits, while using the opportunities for regular personal contact, e.g. events, network meetings, to maintain network effectiveness. Scale interaction intensity according to specific needs:
 - information exchange: e.g. regular network meetings, thematic round tables, quarterly business breakfasts, annual stakeholder conferences
 - (regular) coordination: e.g. monthly updates, department updates, knowledge sharing, brief check-ins; structured consultations, thematic working groups, regular coordination meetings)
 - active collaboration: consultation on planned actions, participatory decision making, joint project management / implementation partnerships, joint problem-solving / co-creation / design thinking workshops
 - **Provide clear, accurate and up-to-date information** through appropriate platforms to facilitate informed collaboration and innovative solutions. This helps establish mutually beneficial and effective interactions. Assess if there are easy channels for external actors to contact the city administration on the issue in question, and consider establishing one, if there are not.
- Maintaining stakeholder relationships requires efforts and should therefore be planned for explicitly, **defining responsibilities** for this within the main team and **allocating respective resources**.

When mapping the stakeholder landscape, learning about their perspectives and thinking about fruitful and efficient collaboration, your theory of change provides key information. It will help you see where you might need input or support and what form it should take. Stakeholder collaboration can help overcome some of the barriers and gaps identified in terms of alignment of governance levels (e.g. EU stakeholders partially stepping up for lack of national alignment) or of sectors as well as in terms of instruments (e.g. non-government actors supporting certain practices when governmental actors cannot legislate).

Please consult the UP2030 comprehensive efforts on stakeholder engagement for inspiration. Among others, the project has used the following **tools**:

- a [Citizen Mapping Tool](#) - an inclusive, web-based, open-source platform designed to collect qualitative, spatial information from citizens and local urban stakeholders
- a [Spatial Justice package](#) with a variety of tools to integrate justice dimensions into urban planning
- [Community Maps](#), a mobile-friendly web platform that supports participatory urban planning by enabling stakeholders to collaboratively map and visualize their neighbourhoods.

Among a great variety of stakeholder mapping and engagement **methodologies** available, these – including examples from European municipalities – might be helpful to start:

- [The New European Bauhaus Toolbox](#) offer several pertinent methods for different phases of collaboration and examples of local initiatives where these were tested (see).
- The [URBACT toolkit](#) provides hands-on material for identifying and engaging stakeholders.
- [WWF's "Public Engagement Guide for Cities"](#) with best-practice examples from European cities
- The ["Governance City Planning and Strategy Handbook for citizen-centric, resilient and safe cities"](#) with a comprehensive overview of methodologies as well as European best practices

- The [Citizen Engagement in Climate Action](#) manual is guides regional and local authorities on how to engage stakeholders throughout the six main steps of the planning process

Furthermore, the following city **networks** focussing on transformation might be of interest to explore existing best practice and connect with urban transformation practitioners: [Climate City Contracts](#), [Friends of NEB](#), [URBACT](#), [Resilient Cities Network](#), [ClimateAdapt Community of Practice](#).

5. **Cater to Vulnerable and Under-Represented Groups:** For every public action, it is key to identify population groups that are especially **vulnerable** and/or **underrepresented** (e.g. elderly, low-income, people with disabilities, minorities). These groups tend to overlap but might also be different, e.g. while elderly people might be more vulnerable, there perspectives and needs might be well-represented and understood, while it might be the other way around for migrant communities. The **impacts of envisioned actions on different population groups** should be systematically assessed, with particular attention to vulnerable communities. This is a basis to analyse what an equitable distribution of benefits looks like (it might mean some groups need more attention or a different approach) and helps prevent unintended negative consequences.

When planning your task, it might be useful to establish **specific procedures** of including diverse perspectives to make sure the differentiated impacts remain on your radar. For this, consider ways to involve these groups throughout the process, systematically and on a regular basis. Methods can encompass direct participation such as participatory budgeting, community workshops, focus groups, online consultations, written feedback, or alternative methods (usually less resource-intensive) such as customer journey mapping, persona-method, social impact assessments, representative surveys. Choose **suitable formats** depending on the process phase and the input needed: direct engagement (focus group discussions, community forums, regular consultations, co-creating formats), representative input (advocacy group meetings, feedback from social service providers), research (e.g. questionnaires, interviews).

Please consult the [UP2030 tools](#) on inclusive participation and social justice, among others:

- a [social justice package](#), developed by TU Delft, with a variety of tools to integrate justice dimensions into urban planning
- the [Child and Youth-Friendly Urban Design Framework](#) (CYFUD), developed by Design Clips, a conceptual framework with flexible toolkits designed to ensure the inclusion of children and young people in urban design and planning, tailored to specific city or neighbourhood projects. Building on child-centred participatory research, the manual translates child-friendly street indicators into practical design strategies.
- [Community Maps](#), by Mapping for Change, a mobile-friendly web platform that supports participatory urban planning by enabling stakeholders to collaboratively map and visualize their neighbourhoods.

Helpful **material** on scoping and involving vulnerable and underrepresented groups is available here:

- The [Inclusive Community Engagement Playbook](#) by C40 shares best practice in inclusive engagement and provides cities with a practical guide to engage their communities in climate action, particularly those hard-to-reach and often excluded groups.
- The UNDP [Checklist for Gender Responsive, Socially Inclusive Stakeholder Consultations](#) can help ensure a gender-responsive, culturally sensitive, non-discriminatory and inclusive consultation process, identifying potentially affected vulnerable and marginalized groups and can participate effectively.
- The [Good Practice Guidelines for Engaging with People with Disability](#) cover many specific ways of making policy processes accessible during their design, planning and implementation, as part of Australia's Disability Strategy 2021-2031.

- The [Inclusive Meeting Guide](#) by the Harvard University provides a brief and practical overview of specific steps to take for an inclusive and effective participation.
- The ICLEI's "[City toolkit: The role of local government in advancing a just transition in the built environment](#)" demonstrates how local governments can coordinate policies across different governance levels to both decarbonise and make the built environment more equitable. By leveraging tools such as co-design with communities and partnerships with businesses, cities can ensure that climate action also addresses social inclusion and stakeholder needs.

Some urban **best practice** examples are:

- As part of the EU-funded EmPaci project (Empowering Participatory Budgeting in the Baltic Sea Region), participating municipalities from several countries carried out a conceptual exercise applying the [customer journey](#) method to the participatory budgeting process in Bützow, Germany. This theoretical framework created a fictional persona, 'Gabi Müller', a 27-year-old mother and part-time supermarket worker, to illustrate how citizens might experience such initiatives. This analysis suggested that multi-channel communication would be essential, combining traditional letters with face-to-face promotion at local festivals and a user-friendly online platform. By encouraging municipalities to view citizens as 'customers' of government services, this theoretical exercise aimed to demonstrate how participatory budgeting initiatives could become more responsive and citizen-centred.
 - Duisburg's 2024 Local action plan for housing ([Social Report 2024 Focus topic: Social and climate-friendly Development of the housing landscape in Duisburg - Local action plan for housing](#) in German) update exemplifies inclusive urban planning. It focuses on socially and climate-friendly housing development, integrating climate adaptation with social equity. A diverse project group, including representatives of vulnerable groups (social organizations, welfare organisations) and other key stakeholders (housing industry, tenant representatives, housing experts), participated in five work meetings, including three thematic workshops.
6. **Involve the Private Sector:** Not all public action is suitable for private sector support; however, it is always worthwhile to explore the perspectives of businesses to avoid blind spots and better understand their interests. These interests may align with public objectives, creating opportunities for synergies with businesses, associations, and financial institutions. The private sector can provide valuable insights into potential conflicts of interest and help shape actions, so they are more compatible with business activities. By developing a deeper **understanding of private sector perspectives**, municipalities can design frameworks that attract and facilitate financial or other support to community initiatives, while safeguarding public benefit through appropriate oversight mechanisms.

Such collaboration can take the form of **formal partnerships** (e.g. public-private partnerships, joint funding schemes, cooperation agreements) or **informal arrangements** (e.g. voluntary participation programmes, support initiatives, awareness campaigns). When involving the private sector in stakeholder processes, cooperation formats can be jointly selected based on shared objectives and implementation capacity, with a focus on practical solutions that benefit both public and private partners. Furthermore, municipalities can assess their scope to establish rules and incentives that encourage sustainable solutions — for example, by incorporating such requirements into permitting procedures or offering preferential treatment.

To explore several financing options for your project and involvement of the private sector, the **Sustainable Business Canvas** method can be a good place to start (p. 40 of [the New European Bauhaus Toolbox](#)). It enables project teams to think about suitable project business model and how this can contribute to environmental sustainability, enhance social well-being, and create economic value. How to involve the private sector in a way that makes sense is a part of this exercise.

Some examples on the roles of the private sector in municipal action are:

- The County of **Munich** established a climate funds “[Aktion Zukunft+](#)”, a crowdfunding mechanism, where companies, organizations and citizens can purchase climate certificates to support local transformation projects. Each €20 certificate represents one ton of CO₂ and funds are split between local and global climate projects. The initiative has already enabled planting of 12,000 trees and conversion of agricultural land to more sustainable practices through private funding. A dedicated governance board ensures effective project selection and implementation.
- The City of **Warsaw** (Poland) launched in 2021 a [Green Fund for Warsaw](#) as a financing mechanism that allows private companies to support urban greening initiatives through direct funding. Companies can contribute to existing programs or fund new greening projects, with clear processes for project selection and implementation.
- The “[Public-Private Collaboration Guide for Global South Cities](#)” provides examples and a practical framework for private sector partnership on large-scale, transformative urban projects, focusing on shared objectives, transparent processes, and risk-sharing. It offers step-by-step recommendations for structuring partnerships, engaging stakeholders, and ensuring sustainable outcomes throughout the project lifecycle.

7. **Promote Productive Multi-Level Exchange:** Multiple levels of governance shape urban sustainability action—for example, by providing access to funding—but can also present barriers when higher-level regulations do not align with local needs. **Mapping** the relevant rules, regulations, and responsibilities across different political levels (local, sub-national, national, and EU) is a valuable exercise for identifying both challenges and opportunities.

With this picture in mind, urban practitioners can actively participate in existing coordination frameworks between levels of government (e.g. regional planning committees, state-local working groups, [EU Urban Agenda partnerships](#)) and use networking opportunities (e.g. thematic conference with relevant national / regional / European officials). Where frameworks do not yet exist, you can explore how to **initiate structured dialogue** on your topics through municipal associations or regional bodies. Suitable participation formats can vary based on relevance and resources, from individual liaisons at higher governance levels to regular committee meetings to formal multi-level coordination processes.

Helpful material was developed by C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group: The [Vertically-Integrated Climate Action Toolkit](#) helps cities and national governments coordinate climate policies, plans, and implementation across different levels of government. The toolkit includes diagnostic, strategy-setting, and implementation tools—such as the Excel-based Vertically-Integrated Action Tool (VIA Tool), a guiding framework for response strategies, and a protocol template for formal agreements—to identify and address barriers and opportunities for vertical integration in climate action. These resources support cities in aligning efforts, improving collaboration, and effectively delivering Climate Action Plans through enhanced coordination between local, regional, and national authorities.

Some examples of how different EU countries organise multi-level interaction are:

- German Conference of Ministers for Urban Development (Bauministerkonferenz): This federal-state conference brings together representatives from Germany’s federal government, the 16 states (Länder), and municipal associations to coordinate urban development policy. At the [17th Congress in Heidelberg](#), representatives from all levels of government, city networks, and civil society convened to explore new forms of collaboration and alliances. Regular meetings enable alignment of strategies, joint working groups, and the negotiation of funding programmes such as the “[Urban Development Support](#)”.

- In France, multi-level “[City Contracts](#)” bring together local, regional, and national authorities to coordinate urban renewal and social cohesion policies in disadvantaged neighbourhoods to address urban inequalities and drive integrated transformation. These contracts shall define shared priorities, financial commitments, and monitor mechanisms for all levels of government.
- [The Swedish Association of Local Authorities and Regions \(SALAR\)](#) demonstrates a bridge between local, regional, and national levels, to facilitate knowledge exchange, joint advocacy, and policy alignment for innovation and sustainability. This approach reflects both multi-level and polycentric governance, enabling Swedish cities and regions to collaborate, learn, and influence policy across multiple governance centres.
- The [Multi-stakeholder and multi-level governance page by Portico](#) highlights the importance of coordinated action across different governance levels (local, regional, national) and offers several short examples from European cities.

8. **Use a Smart Instrument Mix:** Based on your theory of change, that is, your vision of change and your assumptions of how this can be achieved, you can analyse what instruments are needed and which are already available. A balanced mix of measures is often most effective, with actions that complement one another through a **mutually supportive interaction** of different instruments. These may include informational tools (such as awareness-raising campaigns and educational initiatives), partnership arrangements (such as cooperation frameworks), economic incentives (such as grants and taxation), legal regulations (such as mandatory standards and bans), and strategic approaches (such as planning guidance and action plans). These instruments can also be introduced gradually, depending on what is feasible within a given timeframe and how a selection of measures can be progressively expanded to address new topics.

Existing instruments—such as building codes, zoning regulations, public-private partnership frameworks, and educational guidelines and programmes—can serve as effective levers for integrating sustainability considerations. In addition, the actions, measures, and instruments implemented by actors outside the municipality can provide important entry points for promoting transformation within the field.

Involving **different municipality units, civil society and the private sector** in discussing what instruments work well and what might be missing can offer a more comprehensive picture and help source innovative ideas. Available best practice from across Europe as well as from your networks can offer a starting point for these discussions.

European cities provide good examples of comprehensive instrument mix to promote sustainable transformation:

- Copenhagen's comprehensive approach to [promoting cycling](#), using a mix of hard (infrastructure, regulation) and soft (information, partnerships) measures.
- Amsterdam leverages a balanced mix of regulatory, partnership, and knowledge-sharing instruments to foster a [circular economy](#). Through initiatives like the Circular Denim Deal and [Green Deals](#), and investments of over €14 million for the [Amsterdam Implementation Agenda 2023- 2026](#), the city brings together businesses, research institutions, and citizens to remove regulatory barriers, promote sustainable procurement, and scale up innovative solutions.
- [Leuven](#) demonstrates how a city can effectively combine policy instruments to drive ambitious climate adaptation (CCA) and nature-based solutions. The policy portfolio covers a spectrum of interventions—from unsealing and greening public squares and roads to promoting green roofs and facades. The example illustrates how regulation (e.g., spatial planning limits on parking), subsidies (for greening private land), and soft support (such as free pavement removal and practical guidance) work together.

- Learning and Capacity Building: Through initiatives like the LIFE Participation Hub and the [JUSTNature project, Leuven](#) invests in strategic learning, sharing best practices, and fostering innovation through multi-stakeholder processes. This ensures that local action is informed by broader European experience and scientific evidence.
- London’s [Ultra Low Emission Zone \(ULEZ\)](#) uses a smart instrument mix of legal regulation (strict emission standards), economic incentives (charges for polluting vehicles), and extensive public information campaigns to improve air quality. This approach is highlighted as a leading best practice in the Clean Cities Campaign’s [“Low Emission Zones Essential Guide”](#), which showcases how such zones drive urban transformation and healthier cities.
- With its [Smart City Framework Strategy 2019 - 2050](#) (see especially pp. 148ff) Vienna employs a comprehensive instrument mix, which includes urban planning guidelines, building codes, innovation partnerships, financial incentives for energy efficiency, and ongoing stakeholder engagement. The city is advancing long-term sustainability and social inclusion by integrating strategic planning with legal requirements and economic support. The [strategy](#)'s participatory and adaptive design enables new solutions to be introduced and scaled up gradually.

9. **Encourage Innovation:** When considering which existing instruments and measures to enhance or add, it is valuable to focus on how they can drive innovation, as this is a key catalyst for transformation. Attention should be given to the elements—either through new initiatives or by adapting existing instruments—to promote and facilitate innovative thinking and experimentation among both public and private actors. This might include knowledge-sharing and exchange formats, regular idea competitions, cross-sectoral collaboration, and co-creation with end users. You can highlight the question of fostering innovation in your stakeholder consultations to explore their thinking and harness their experience on the matter.

Please consult some examples of fostering innovation:

- The [Stuttgart Climate Innovation Fund](#) supports innovative projects that contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and a climate-friendly city. It supports companies, start-ups, research institutions and civil society organisations in developing and implementing effective climate protection solutions. Funded projects must be implemented in Stuttgart.
- The City of Sofia has implemented a successful model for promoting private sector engagement and stimulating innovation and modernisation through its [Sandbox for Innovative Solutions](#) programme. Launched by Innovative Sofia, the municipality's digitalization and innovation unit, the city identifies specific challenge areas where innovation is needed - such as urban mobility, e-services, or environmental solutions. Local businesses and entrepreneurs can then propose and test their solutions in real urban conditions, with the municipality providing necessary infrastructure access and regulatory support. This targeted approach ensures that entrepreneurial innovation directly addresses the city's most pressing needs.
- The [RESPONSE project hackathons](#) in Turku and Dijon generated innovative solutions for pressing challenges like energy transition and mobility, empowering cities to lead with cutting-edge ideas. By fostering collaboration and creative problem-solving, hackathons help transform lighthouse cities into hubs of innovation and sustainability, inspiring others to join the movement towards a greener future.
- The Digitallotsen programme is an innovative initiative aimed at accelerating digital transformation in German municipalities and administrations. It involves training individuals within the administration who are enthusiastic about digital issues and motivated to drive change to become the so-called digital pilots (e.g. in [Konstanz](#)).
- The [European Urban Initiative](#), the follow-up of the Urban Innovative Action initiative, collects examples of urban innovative action on its platform.

10. **Clarify Roles and Responsibilities and Enable their Fulfilment:** Once the tasks and the necessary steps are clear, it is important to specify and communicate the precise roles and responsibilities of all relevant units. This ensures that everyone understands their part in the process. Consider organising a joint kick-off discussion to clarify these roles, as well as regular ‘stop-and-reflect’ meetings to assess collaboration and progress. Support these efforts with accessible documentation of key procedures and workflows. Strive for structures that are both clear and flexible, able to accommodate routine operations as well as unexpected challenges. Assess how existing structures—such as regular meetings, committees, and designated positions—can be utilised effectively, and determine when new structures may be necessary.

Helpful material on assigning roles and responsibilities is:

- This [URBACT tool](#) guides users through designing effective project implementation structures.
- A quick way to assign responsibilities is to use the [RACI matrix](#) – which defines who is responsible, accountable, consulted and informed on each individual action.

Leuven implements its Climate Adaptation Plan (2020-2025) through multiple city departments working together on cross-cutting issues such as greening the city or improving mobility (see [case study](#), pp. 14). At the same time, every climate change adaptation project is “owned” by a specific department or individual, responsible for driving the project forward, while others have clearly defined supporting roles.

11. **Strive for an Adequate Budget:** Ensuring that tasks are supported by adequate financial means is a common challenge for municipalities, that often need to bring budgets for activities together from **diverse sources**. This requires regular review mechanisms to monitor and adjust resources as necessary, thus maintaining financial flexibility. If there is no specific budget line assigned to your task, screening the options of financing parts of the activities under other budget lines, existing project funding as well as defining a budget acquisition/allocation strategy or a business case can be first steps.

European platforms and networks for sustainable municipal action can often be a first entry points to find experts in your region that are experienced with different models of financing. The financial aspect can also play a prominent role in **stakeholder engagement**, serving to gather ideas and foster collaboration. If certain activities can only be budgeted in later phases, developing an overarching vision and a detailed implementation plan—e.g. operationalised as clear procurement guidelines—can help ensure the project remains consistent and coherent.

In the UP2030 project, GGGI developed financing tools. The Cost-Benefit Assessment Guide (CBA Guide) helps cities identify the best-fit CBA tool based on their technical capacity, data availability, and project type. It simplifies the selection and use of existing CBA tools, helping cities assess both monetary and non-monetary benefits, and build stronger, evidence-based investment cases. The Green Finance Guide helps cities identifying and leveraging appropriate financial instruments and funding sources. It provides an overview of both conventional and innovative financing tools, guidance on how to combine them effectively (for relevant instruments), and examples of how they’ve been used in urban contexts (case studies).

Helpful material on acquiring finance and building business cases is available here.

- The [URBACT toolkit](#) includes a comprehensive set of tools on resourcing, from assessing the needs to specific costing and strategies to acquire funding.
- The Sustainable Business Canvas method (p. 40 of [the New European Bauhaus Toolbox](#)) enables project teams to think about suitable business models for their project and how

this can contribute to environmental sustainability, enhance social well-being, and create economic value. It helps a group to brainstorm

[Leuven](#) demonstrates how a city can effectively combine funding streams to drive ambitious climate adaptation (CCA) and nature-based solutions. The city leverages municipal, regional, and European funds, each with distinct roles. Local reconstruction budgets, regional climate adaptation investments, and European programmes (like LIFE and Horizon 2020) are strategically combined. This mix allows Leuven to finance both broad infrastructure projects and targeted pilots, ensuring flexibility and resilience in funding.